

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Tursunov Ilxom Rabbimqo'l o'g'li

TIBBIYOT MUASSASALARI HODIMLARINING

RAG'BATLANTIRISH USULLARINI ANIQLASH

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/FEVRAL

